

The MHC class II transactivator modulates seeded alpha-synuclein pathology and dopaminergic neurodegeneration in an *in vivo* rat model of Parkinson's disease

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ABSTRACT

Background: Abnormal folding, aggregation and spreading of alpha-synuclein (α syn) is a mechanistic hypothesis for the progressive neuropathology in Parkinson's disease (PD). Spread of α syn between cells is supported by clinical, neuropathological and experimental evidence. It has been proposed that a pro-inflammatory micro-environment in response to α syn can promote its aggregation. We have previously shown that allelic differences in the major histocompatibility complex class two transactivator (*Mhc2ta*) gene, located in the VRA4 locus, alter MHCII expression levels, microglial activation and antigen presentation capacity in rats upon human α syn over-expression. In addition, *Mhc2ta* regulated dopaminergic neurodegeneration and the extent of motor impairment. The purpose of this study was to determine whether *Mhc2ta* regulates α syn aggregation, propagation and dopaminergic pathology in an α syn pre-formed fibril (PFF)-seeded *in vivo* model of PD.

Methods: The DA and DA.VRA4 congenic rat strains share background genome but display differential microglial antigen presenting capacity due to different *Mhc2ta* alleles in the VRA4 locus. PFFs of human α syn or BSA solution were injected unilaterally to the striatum of DA and DA.VRA4 rats two weeks after ipsilateral administration of recombinant adeno-associated virus (rAAV) vectors carrying human α syn or GFP to the substantia nigra pars compacta. Behavioural assessment was performed at 2, 5 and 8 weeks while histological evaluation of α syn pathology, inflammation and neurodegeneration as well as determination of serum cytokine profiles were performed at 8 weeks.

Results: rAAV-mediated expression of human α syn in nigral dopaminergic neurons combined with striatal PFF administration induced enhanced α syn pathology in DA.VRA4 compared to DA rats. *Mhc2ta* thus significantly regulated the seeding, propagation and toxicity of α syn *in vivo*. This was reflected in terms of wider extent and anatomical distribution of α syn inclusions, ranging from striatum to the forebrain, midbrain, hindbrain and cerebellum in DA.VRA4. Compared to DA rats, DA.VRA4 also displayed enhanced motor impairment and dopaminergic neurodegeneration as well as higher levels of the proinflammatory cytokines IL-2 and TNF α in serum.

Conclusions: We conclude that the key regulator of MHCII expression, *Mhc2ta*, modulates neuroinflammation, α syn-seeded Lewy-like pathology, dopaminergic neurodegeneration and motor impairment. This makes *Mhc2ta* and microglial antigen presentation promising therapeutic targets for reducing the progressive neuropathology and clinical manifestations in PD.

Abbreviations: ANOVA, analyses of variance; AP, anteroposterior; BSA, bovine serum albumin; CL, contralateral; DAB, 3,3'-diaminobenzidine; DV, dorsoventral; GFP, green fluorescent protein; HLA, human leukocyte antigen; Iba1, ionized calcium-binding adapter molecule 1; IL, ipsilateral; Mhc2ta, major histocompatibility complex class II transactivator; MHCII, major histocompatibility complex class II; ML, mediolateral; PD, Parkinson's disease; PFA, paraformaldehyde; PFF, pre-formed fibrils; p α syn, phosphorylated-ser129 α -synuclein; rAAV, recombinant adeno-associated virus; ROI, regions of interest; SEM, standard error of mean; SN, substantia nigra; SNpc, substantia nigra pars compacta; SNPs, single nucleotide polymorphisms; TEM, transmission electron microscopy; TH, tyrosine hydroxylase; α syn, α -synuclein.

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1. Background

Neuropathologically, PD is characterized by a progressive intra-neuronal accumulation of α -synuclein (α syn) in Lewy bodies and Lewy neurites, degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) and neuroinflammation (Spillantini et al., 1998; Braak et al., 2003; McGeer et al., 1988).

The neuroinflammation observed in PD brains includes activation of microglia, up-regulation of major histocompatibility class II (MHCII) molecules, expression of inflammatory mediators and infiltration of T-lymphocytes (McGeer et al., 1988; Brochard et al., 2009; Imamura et al., 2003). These conditions allow activated microglia expressing MHCII to present antigens to CD4-positive (CD4+) T-lymphocytes, and the presence of circulating α syn-reactive CD4+ T-lymphocytes was recently reported in PD patients (Sulzer et al., 2017). Interestingly, several studies have reported genetic risk variants for PD in the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) region encoding MHCII molecules (Wissemann et al., 2013; Lampe et al., 2003; Kannarkat et al., 2015; Hill-Burns et al., 2011; Hamza et al., 2010). These findings strongly support a key role for MHCII and antigen presentation capacity in PD aetiology.

From prodromal to early and late stages of PD, α syn pathology has been described to start in the vagal nerve and brainstem and continue to the midbrain and cortical areas in a pattern that correlates with the progressive symptomatology (Braak et al., 2003). A prion-like seeding where misfolded α syn acts as a template for naive forms is suggested as a mechanism behind the spread of α syn pathology to neighboring cells and brain regions, resulting in neuronal dysfunction and neurodegeneration (Brundin and Melki, 2017). The hypothesis is supported by the observed spread of α syn from host cells to transplants in patients grafted with primary fetal ventral mesencephalic tissue (Li et al., 2008; Kordower et al., 2011, 2008) as well as in primary grafts in mice (Hansen et al., 2011). The prion-like hypothesis has been questioned (Surmeier et al., 2017) but has also led to the development of experimental models for progressive α syn pathology and PD-like neurodegeneration. *In vitro*, administration of aggregated α syn in the form of pre-formed fibrils (PFFs) to cells overexpressing α syn has been shown to induce seeding and the formation of Lewy body-like insoluble inclusions (Luk et al., 2009). *In vivo*, models using aggregated forms of α syn as seeds have been shown to induce a progressive PD-like pathology in rodents (Luk et al., 2012; Rey et al., 2016). Of note, PFF-induced microglial activation and MHCII expression have been shown to precede dopaminergic neurodegeneration and to significantly correlate with the load of phosphorylated-ser129 α syn ($p\alpha$ syn) inclusions in SNpc (Duffy et al., 2018). Recently, a rat model was developed combining viral vector-mediated expression of human α syn, to act as substrate, with local administration of human PFFs, to act as seeds (Thakur et al., 2017). This model recapitulates many of the pathophysiological hallmarks observed in PD, including $p\alpha$ syn inclusions, microgliosis, dopaminergic cell death in SNpc and motor impairment. Compared to α syn-based rat PD models using viral vectors alone (Decressac et al., 2012), models combining viral vectors with PFFs have the advantages of a more physiological level of transgene expression as well as a lower immune response to the viral vector. Compared to striatal administration of PFFs alone, the combined models allow for studies on the mechanisms behind seeded pathology on locally produced human α syn. In addition, the combination enhances and accelerates formation of α syn inclusions as well as degeneration of dopaminergic neurons and behavioural deficits (Paumier et al., 2015).

The activation pattern of microglia in rat PD models has been shown to be dependent on the degree of α syn pathology and neurodegeneration (Sanchez-Guajardo et al., 2010) and we have previously shown that differential MHCII expression regulates α syn-induced microglial activation and dopaminergic neurodegeneration (Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017). The extent of microglial activation, MHCII expression and α syn pathology are thus mutually dependent. The MHCII transactivator (*Mhc2ta*) is the major regulator of MHCII expression on antigen

presenting cells, including microglia and macrophages in the CNS. Variants in the rat *Mhc2ta* promoter region regulate MHCII expression upon nerve injury and the susceptibility to experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (Harnesk et al., 2008; Lidman et al., 2003). Interestingly, corresponding variants in the human *MHC2TA* gene are associated to the risk for multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis and myocardial infarction (Swanberg et al., 2005). With respect to PD, we have recently shown that *Mhc2ta* allelic variants significantly modify MHCII gene expression, microglial activation, dopaminergic neurodegeneration and motor deficits in an α syn over-expression model in rats (Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017). However, if *Mhc2ta* and antigen presentation capacity influence the extent and propagation of α syn pathology is not known. To fill this gap, we have used two congenic rat strains (DA and DA.VRA4) with allelic variants in the *Mhc2ta* gene leading to differential gene expression of *Mhc2ta* and its targets, mainly MHCII genes to determine whether *Mhc2ta* modulates α syn aggregation, propagation and toxicity to dopaminergic neurons.

Our results from a combined model, with a low-titre recombinant adeno-associated viral vector (rAAV) encoding human α syn and administration of PFFs, show that lower *Mhc2ta* levels and reduced antigen presentation capacity is associated with Lewy-like α syn pathology, enhanced α syn anatomical spread, increased dopaminergic neurodegeneration, exacerbated motor impairment and a proinflammatory peripheral cytokine profile. These significant effects of *Mhc2ta* on PD-like pathology, together with previous findings that orthologous variants in the *MHC2TA* gene are associated to human inflammatory diseases, strongly support a role for antigen presentation in PD aetiology and future targeting of inflammatory responses as a promising strategy to prevent α syn pathology and disease progression.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental design

In the current study we compared adult males of the DA and DA.VRA4 rat strains. These congenic strains are genetically identical with the exception of the VRA4 locus on chromosome 10 encoding the *Mhc2ta* gene, resulting in functional but lower MHCII expression levels in DA.VRA4 compared to DA rats (Fig. 1A). Our experimental design deviated from that of Thakur and colleagues (Thakur et al., 2017) in the site of PFF injection (striatum instead of SN) to reduce surgery-induced local inflammatory responses in SN and to study the interaction of substrate (nigrostriatal human α syn transgene expression) and seed (striatal PFF). A schematic of the experimental approach and timeline are given in Fig. 1C. In brief, rats were injected first with rAAV6 vectors carrying human α syn (ASYN) or green fluorescent protein (GFP). Two weeks post-rAAV6 injection, PFF or bovine serum albumin (BSA) was injected into striatal terminal regions of the midbrain dopamine fibres. Midbrain injection of rAAV6-GFP was used to investigate whether virus-driven produced human α syn is required for PFF-induced Lewy body-like inclusions (comparing GFP + PFF and ASYN + PFF groups) and striatal injection of BSA was used to investigate the effect of PFF as a seed for virus-driven produced human α syn (comparing ASYN + BSA and ASYN + PFF groups). This approach resulted in the following groups (n = 10 each): DA ASYN + PFF, DA.VRA4 ASYN + PFF, DA GFP + PFF, DA.VRA4 GFP + PFF, DA ASYN + BSA, DA.VRA4 ASYN + BSA (Fig. 1C). Behavioural phenotypes were assessed at 2, 5, and 8 weeks post rAAV delivery (3- and 6-weeks post PFF/BSA injection). At 8 weeks after rAAV injection, serum and brains were collected.

2.2. Animals

All procedures were conducted in accordance with guidelines set by the Ethics Committee for the use of laboratory animals in the region Lund-Malmö Sweden (M188-14). All animals were housed 2–4 per cage and given *ad libitum* access to food and water during a 12:12 h light/dark

cycle. Sixty adult male rats were included (30 DA and 30 DA.VRA4). The DA.VRA4 congenic rats were generated as previously described (Harnesk et al., 2008) and genotyped accordingly (Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017) (founders kindly provided by Prof. Fredrik Piehl, Karolinska Institute, Stockholm, Sweden).

2.3. Viral vectors

Two titre-matched rAAV6 vectors were used to overexpress either human wild-type α syn or GFP. Both rAAV6 vectors were injected at 1.02×10^{10} gc/ μ l in the midbrain of the experimental animals. The transgenes are under transcriptional control of the synapsin-1 promoter and enhanced using a woodchuck hepatitis virus posttranscriptional regulatory element (Decressac et al., 2012).

2.4. Preformed fibrils and BSA

Preformed fibrils were kindly provided by Prof. Virginia Lee and Dr. Kelvin C. Luk, University of Philadelphia, USA. Purification of recombinant full-length human α syn was prepared as described previously (Luk et al., 2009) and injected 2 weeks after viral vector delivery (10 μ g total, 2 μ l per site). Before injections, the PFFs were thawed and sonicated at room temperature by probe sonication as has been reported

before (Thakur et al., 2017; Volpicelli-Daley et al., 2011) in a sonicator (Qsonica sonicators). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) pictures of PFFs after sonication are presented in Fig. 1B. BSA: Lyophilized BSA was purchased from Sigma (A9418), dissolved in DPBS at 5 mg/ml was used as a control for the PFF injection.

2.5. Surgical procedure

All surgical procedures were performed under 1–2% isoflurane anaesthesia (Isoflo vet, Orion Pharma AB Animal Health, Sweden) in a 2:1 O₂:NO mixture. Marcain (Apoteksbolaget, Stockholm, Sweden) was used as local anaesthetic. In brief, rats were placed in a stereotaxic frame (Kopf Instruments) and the vector solution was injected using a 10 μ l Hamilton syringe fitted with a glass capillary (outer diameter of 250 μ m). Intranigral injections (3 μ l) were performed at the following coordinates given in mm relative to Bregma and dural surface (Paxinos et al., 1980) with the incisor bar set at –2.3 mm below the interaural line: anteroposterior (AP): –5.3; mediolateral (ML): –1.7; dorsoventral (DV): –7.2. Intrastratial injections (2.5 μ l per site) were made at the following coordinates; site 1: AP: +0.1; ML: –3.0; DV: –5.0 and site 2: AP: –0.4; ML: –3.0; DV: –4.5. All injections were performed at a constant flow rate of 0.2 μ l per minute. The capillary was left in place for 2 min after injection to allow for diffusion before carefully retracting the

Fig. 1. Experimental design. A. Representative images of MHCII immunoreactive cells in the striatum of DA and DA.VRA4 rats after rAAV- α syn and PFF injections demonstrating the lower levels of MHCII expression in the DA.VRA4 congenic strain (scale bar = 10 μ m). B. Representative TransEM images of PFFs before (left) and after (right) sonication and resuspension in DPBS (scale bar = 100 μ m). C. Experimental design and study timeline. D. Representative images of α syn expression throughout the midbrain and striatum of DA and DA.VRA4 rats receiving injections of rAAV- α syn in the substantia nigra and PFFs in the striatum.

injection capillary. After closing the wound, we provided post-operative analgesia by s.c. injection of 0.15 ml Metacam (Apoteksbolaget, Stockholm, Sweden). All animals were then placed in clean cages on a heated pad for recovery and monitored for the coming 48 h.

2.6. Motor impairment assessment

To evaluate motor activity, forelimb akinesia (Olsson et al., 1995) was determined in the animals using the stepping test at 2, 5 and 8 weeks after vector injection. The same experimenter, blinded to the group-identity, performed each test in the same testing room, at the same interval during the day. The cages were tested in random order during the experiment days. At the initiation of the experiment, the animals were habituated and previously trained in the test for 3 days. Briefly, the experimenter moved the rat horizontally over a fixed distance (90 cm) for 3 trials per day. Steps for each forelimb were recorded and averaged across trials. Data are presented as the average number of adjusting steps made by the forepaw contralateral to the injection side. Before the first time point, the animals were habituated and pre-trained in the test for 3 days.

2.7. Serum and tissue preparation

Eight weeks after intranigral injection peripheral blood was drawn by cardiac puncture in animals under 0.2 ml sodium pentobarbital intraperitoneal anaesthesia (200 mg/kg). After collection, blood was left undisturbed at room temperature for 30 min to allow the blood to coagulate. Serum was isolated by centrifugation (2.000g, 10 min, 4 °C), transfer into a new Eppendorf tube and stored at –80 °C until analysis. Immediately after cardiac puncture, animals were transcardially perfused with 50 ml 0.9% saline, followed by 250 ml ice-cold paraformaldehyde (4% pH 7.4). The brains were collected and post-fixed in 4% PFA overnight and then cryoprotected in 30% sucrose (in PBS, with 0.01% sodium azide).

2.8. Bright-field Immunohistochemistry, immunofluorescence, confocal microscopy

The brains were sectioned coronally on a freezing microtome (Microm HM 450, Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) at 35 µm and stored them in antifreeze solution at 4 °C until immunostaining. Bright-field Immunohistochemical stainings were performed on free-floating sections at room temperature using primary antibodies and secondary biotinylated antibodies listed in Table 1. A full description of the staining procedure can be found in (Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017). A standard peroxidase-based method was used (Vectastain ABC kit and DAB; Vector Laboratories). Initially, sections were quenched with 3% H₂O₂/10% MetOH for 30 min, blocked with 5% serum, accordingly with the secondary antibody before overnight incubation with primary antibody at RT. On the second day, sections were incubated with the

corresponding biotinylated secondary antibody for 1 h at RT. Followed by a 30-min incubation with an avidin-biotin peroxidase solution (ABC Elite, Vector Laboratories). For the visualisation of the secondary antibody sections were developed using 3'-diaminobenzide (DAB) and Peroxide (3%). After mounted on gelatine-coated slides, the sections were air-dried overnight, dehydrated in a series of ascending concentration of ethanol and xylene and cover slipped with DPX mounting medium (Sigma-Aldrich, Gillingham). Proteinase K digestion was performed on mounted sections. Briefly, sections were incubated for 1 h with Proteinase K (5 µg/ml, Thermo Scientific), diluted in 0.05 M TRIS-buffered saline at pH 7.6. Following Proteinase K digestion, the same procedure described above as for free-floating sections was followed.

For fluorescent microscopy, stainings were performed on free-floating sections and were blocked with 5% Normal goat serum before overnight incubation with primary antibody (Table 1) at 4 °C. On the second day, sections were incubated with the corresponding fluorescent secondary antibody for 1 h at RT. Stained sections were mounted on gelatine-coated slides and secured with coverslips using PVA-DABCO (Sigma). Confocal images were acquired on a Leica SP8 confocal microscope under a 20× objective using the same settings for all sections.

2.9. Densitometry analysis of Dopaminergic Fibre Loss in the Striatum

Striatal TH+ fibre optical density was determined using the ImageJ software (Version 1.49, NIH, USA) at four coronal levels (1.60, 0.48, –0.26 and –0.40 mm relative to Bregma). The photomicrographs were obtained using a Light microscope (Olympus BX53, Tokyo, Japan) at 2× magnification. Each image was analysed using the optical density (O.D.) values obtained from the Rodbard calibration curve after being transformed into grey-scale image. The TH+ fibres density was determined by the mean grey and was normalized by measuring and subtracting background staining optical density from the corpus callosum for each animal. The data are presented as percentage of contralateral side density. From a total of 60 animals, an average of 3 animals were excluded from the analysis due to complications during surgery or with tissue processing, leaving 20 DA and 19 DA.VRA4 for analysis.

2.10. Axonal swelling quantification

Four sections from each animal at Bregma distance 1.60, 0.48, –0.26 and –0.40 were analysed. High-resolution z-stack 25× magnification images were taken using a Light microscope (Olympus BX53, Tokyo, Japan). Two pictures were taken of each section representing the dorsal and ventral part of the caudate putamen of striatum for every section. ImageJ software (Version 1.49, NIH, USA) was used to identify the TH+ swellings and calculate the total number of swellings, and their size. Each image was analysed after being transformed into grey-scale image. The number of TH+ swellings was determined by particle analysis function. The average number of TH+ swellings were calculated based on all the pictures from one animal. A genotype-blind operator performed image acquisition and quantification.

2.11. Alpha-synuclein aggregation / deposition / scoring of pathology

For histological mapping analysis immunoreactive p_αsyn + inclusions/cells and neurites were mapped as previously described (Luk et al., 2012) in rostral to caudal levels. The presence of p_αsyn-positive (p_αsyn+) accumulations was assessed in a blinded manner by two independent researchers screening every section at 20× in a Light microscope (Olympus BX53, Tokyo, Japan). For histological scoring of p_αsyn-positive (p_αsyn+) pathology an adapted version of a previously described scoring scale (Rey et al., 2016) based on the presence of immunoreactivity for p_αsyn+ accumulations patterns was used; 0: no aggregates; 1: sparse (very few neurites, max one nuclear deposit, scattered dot-like inclusions); 2: mild (varicose and filiform neurites, with or without presence of nuclear deposits); 3: moderate (many

Table 1

List of antibodies used.

Antigen/Secondary antibody	Company	Host	Dilution
αsyn (211)	Santa Cruz (sc-12767)	Mouse	1:1000
GFP	Abcam (ab13970)	Chicken	1:1000
p _α syn (pS129)	Abcam (EP1536Y)	Rabbit	1:2000
TH	Millipore (AB152)	Rabbit	1:1000
Iba1	Abcam (ab139590)	Chicken	1:1000
MHCII	Abcam (ab23990)	Mouse	1:500
Biotinylated anti-rabbit	Vector laboratories	Horse	1:200
Biotinylated anti-mouse	Vector laboratories	Goat	1:200
Alexa 647 anti-mouse	Abcam (ab150119)	Goat	1:200
Alexa 488 anti-rabbit	Abcam (ab150081)	Goat	1:200
Alexa 594 anti-chicken	Abcam (ab150176)	Goat	1:200

nuclear and perinuclear, neurites, large areas with dot-like inclusions); 4: many nuclear, perinuclear, filiform neurites and Lewy neurite-like; 5: many perinuclear deposits, Lewy neurite-like and dot-like inclusions; 6: many Lewy bodies-like and Lewy neurites-like inclusions. Representative examples of the different aggregates are illustrated in Fig. 2. The analysis was carried out under 100× magnification using a Leica microscope connected to a digital camera (Leica MPS52) on the ipsilateral side of the brain by a genotype-blind operator using 12 sections/animal through the brain (AP +4.68 to AP −10.32) for each section at the levels mentioned above (Fig. 2D). Data is shown as average grades values at each level from each animal.

2.12. Stereological counts of dopaminergic cells in SNpc

Dopaminergic neuron loss in the SNpc was determined by unbiased stereological estimations of the TH+ cells in SNpc according to the optical fractionator principle as describe elsewhere (Kurowska et al., 2016). An observer blinded to the genotype of the animal performed the counts every sixth section (section sampling fraction, $ssf = 6$) covering the full extent of the SNpc (−4.04 to −7.56 from Bregma) yielding 8–10 sections per animal. Counts were performed employing MicroBrightfield stereological investigator software (Stereo Investigator, MBF Bioscience, V10, US) under 100x magnification using a Leica microscope connected to a digital camera (Leica MPS52). Tracing regions of interest (ROIs) was done using a 5X/0.11 lens, and counting was performed with a 100X/1.30 lens. A series of counting frames (80 μm × 80 μm) was systematically and randomly distributed over grid (180 μm × 180 μm) placed over SNpc. The total population estimate was calculated using optical fractionator estimates. A maximal Gundersen coefficient error (CE) of 0.08 was accepted for cells to be counted. Sections with uneven, blurry, not penetrating staining were excluded from the analysis leaving 18 DA and 18 DA.VRA4 for quantification.

2.13. Semi-quantitative analysis of MHCII+ cells

To quantify MHCII+ cells, 4 equally z-stack images were acquired using a bright-field microscope (Olympus BX53, Tokyo, Japan). The regions of interest were digitalized at a 20x objective, an image matrix of 1024 × 1024 pixel and a pixel scaling of 0.2 × 0.2 μm. The number of MHCII+ cells in striatum or SN was obtained from each photomicrograph using ImageJ software (Version 1.49, NIH, USA) point tool. Photomicrographs were transformed into 8-bit images, with removal of the background and increment of the black and white contrast. The number of positive cells was registered. Immunopositive cells close to the site of injection or needle tract were excluded in order to analyse the response to αsyn rather than tissue damage. Data is shown as average values from 4 striatal and 4 nigral sections for each animal.

2.14. Cytokine analysis

Serum concentrations (pg/ml) of IFNγ, IL-1β, IL-2, IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL-12 and TNFα were determine using MSD multiplex assay platform (Meso Scale Diagnostics, Rockville, MD, USA). The assay was performed according to manufacturer's protocol. Briefly, the plate was loaded with 50 μl per well of controls and unknown samples (diluted 1:2), incubated for 2 h at room temperature with shaking at 800 rpm, washed 3 times with PBS 1× - Tween 20 0.1%, 25 μl of detection antibody was added per well for 2 h with shaking at 800 rpm at room temperature, washed 3 times with PBS 1× - Tween 20 0.1%. The plate was developed using the 4× reading buffer diluted 1 time with dH₂O and analysed using the QuickPlex Q120 reader from Mesoscale. The detection ranges of the different cytokines measured were as follows: IL1β (1670–0.408 pg/mL), IL4 (1660–0.405 pg/mL), IL12 (32200–7.86 pg/mL), IL10 (3410–0.833 pg/mL), IFNγ (938–0.229 pg/mL), IL2 (2630–0.642 pg/mL), IL5 (967–0.236 pg/mL), IL6 (5720–1.40), KC/GRO (homologue to human IL8, 1980–0.483 pg/mL) and TNFα

(627–0.153 pg/mL).

2.15. Electron microscopy

The nature of fibrillar αsyn forms was assessed using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis. The fibril sample (3 μl) was spotted onto a freshly glow-discharged carbon-coated electron microscopy grid. After 1 min, 6 μl uranyl acetate (2% in aqueous solution) was applied to the grid for 2 min. The excessive stain was removed by a filter paper. The samples were imaged using a FEI T12 Tecnai Spirit BioTWIN electron microscope.

2.16. Statistical analysis

Statistical tests were conducted using the GraphPad software (package INC. Version 8.0 La Jolla, USA). Data are expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM) and groups were compared using analyses of variance (ANOVA) and post hoc Tukey's test correction for multiple comparisons. P-values and F-ratios are given in the figure legends. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons are reported in both results and figure legends as being either significant or non-significant. A significance level of $\alpha \leq 0.05$ was chosen for all analyses.

3. Results

To investigate the impact of antigen presentation on the extent and consequences of αsyn pathology, we compared two congenic rat strains with naturally occurring variants in the *Mhc2ta* gene. These variants make the DA.VRA4 strain express lower transcripts levels of *Mhc2ta* and MHCII (Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017) as well as lower MHCII protein levels compared to DA (Fig. 1A). To study aggregation, propagation and toxicity of αsyn, an *in vivo* seeding model combining rAAV6-αsyn and human αsyn PFFs was used. The PFFs were sonicated (Fig. 1B) and injected in the striatum two weeks after rAAV6-αsyn or rAAV6-GFP delivery to the SNpc (Fig. 1C). The rAAV6 vectors mediated strong αsyn or GFP transgene expression, with no differences observed between the treatment groups or between the two strains (Fig. 1D, Supplementary Fig. 1).

3.1. PFFs induce widespread propagation of αsyn pathology in rats expressing human αsyn

To assess the propagation of αsyn pathology we analysed the immunoreactivity to pαsyn, the predominant posttranslational modification occurring in synucleinopathies (Fujiwara et al., 2002), throughout the brain at 8 weeks after rAAV6-αsyn delivery to the SN (6 weeks after PFF injection to the striatum). PFFs induced widespread pαsyn immunoreactivity throughout the rostro-caudal axis, including motor cortex, insular cortices, thalamus, amygdala and cerebellum in rats expressing the human αsyn transgene (Fig. 2A). Despite the fact that PFFs were injected unilaterally, pαsyn positive intraneuronal and neuritic accumulations were present bilaterally in the cortex but remained ipsilateral to the injection site in the SN (Fig. 2A).

We subsequently compared the effects of PFF alone (seeding effect) and the effect of αsyn-overexpression alone (substrate effect) on the induction and spreading of pαsyn-pathology. In rats overexpressing GFP, thus lacking endogenously produced human αsyn, PFFs induced pαsyn immunoreactivity in close proximity to the striatal injection site and in SN (Supplementary Fig. 2.1 A). In rats overexpressing human αsyn and receiving striatal BSA injections, strong pαsyn immunoreactivity was observed in the SN but only minor staining in other brain regions (Supplementary Fig. 2.2C). Thus, the presence of human αsyn substrate, in the form of transgene expression in SN dopaminergic neurons, enhances the propagation of αsyn pathology seeded by striatal administration of PFFs.

Fig. 2. Striatal injection of PFFs combined with nigral α syn overexpression induces widespread α syn pathology (posyn) in the brain. **A.** Map showing the distribution of posyn immunoreactivity (aggregates and neurites as red dots and lines, respectively) in coronal sections from animals sacrificed at 8 weeks post PFF injection. Representative plots are shown for DA and DA.VRA4 animals injected with rAAV- α syn in substantia nigra and PFFs in striatum. **B.** Photomicrographs of positive posyn immunoreactivity of various CNS regions, 3 different striatal (B1-B6) and nigral levels (B7-B12), cerebellum (B13, B16), motor cortex (B14, B17), insular cortex (B15, B18), olfactory tubercle (B19, B22), amygdala (B20, B23) and thalamus (B21, B24) regions are shown. Scale bar = 25 μ m. **C.** Scoring scheme illustrating the anatomical distribution of posyn pathology and aggregation pattern after nigral injection of rAAV- α syn or rAAV-GFP followed by striatal injection of PFFs or BSA. Scoring was performed on 20 DA and 19 DA.VRA4 rats ($n = 6-7$ per group). Scale bar = 10 μ m. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.2. Lower MHCII expression in DA.VRA4 rats enhances *α*syn propagation and inclusion formation

Formation of *α*syn inclusions was detected in all experimental groups and were most abundant close to the sites of injection (Fig. 2A, B; Supplementary Figs. 2.1 and 2.2). In rats expressing human *α*syn and seeded with PFFs (ASYN + PFF), the DA.VRA4 strain displayed more *α*syn-positive inclusions and a larger spread of the pathology compared to DA (Fig. 2A, B). In addition to the localization and amount of aggregates, the deposition pattern of *α*syn differed between the two strains. While DA rats displayed filiform neurites but no round inclusions, DA.VRA4 rats displayed Lewy-like aggregates and neurites located mainly in the striatum (Fig. 2B1 to B6) and midbrain (Fig. 2B7 to B12), but also in brain regions distal to injection sites (Fig. 2B13–B24).

DA and DA.VRA4 rats receiving GFP + PFF or ASYN + BSA, displayed fewer *α*syn-immunoreactive cells but an anatomical distribution similar to rats receiving ASYN + PFF. More cells with inclusions were observed in the midbrain (Supplementary Fig. 2B7–B12 and D7–D12) compared to other brain regions (Supplementary Fig. 2B1–B24 and D1–D24).

The *α*syn inclusions were insoluble as determined by Proteinase K digestion (Supplementary Fig. 3). To further characterize the type of *α*syn inclusions they were characterized as dot-like, nuclear, perinuclear, filiform neurite, varicose neurite, Lewy neurite-like, and Lewy body-like structures and scored according to a modified rating scale (Rey et al., 2016) along the rostro-caudal axis (Fig. 2C). DA.VRA4 rats displayed enhanced inclusion formation compared to DA, both when receiving ASYN + PFF and ASYN + BSA (Fig. 2C), indicating that reduced antigen presenting capacity lead to enhanced seeding and aggregation of *α*syn.

As expected, rats in the GFP + PFF or ASYN + BSA groups displayed smaller deposits, less broken somas and thinner neurites compared to the ASYN + PFF groups, and lower levels of *α*syn pathology was observed distal to the injection sites in the control groups (Fig. 2C). These findings suggest that the model employed is suitable to study both biological effects and extent of *α*syn pathology *in vivo*.

3.3. Seeding of human *α*syn enhances dopaminergic neurodegeneration in rats with reduced *Mhc2ta* expression levels

Neurodegeneration in the form of reduced level of TH+ fibres in the striatum ipsilateral to injections related to the contralateral side was observed in all treatment groups. While similar levels of dopaminergic fibres remained in DA and DA.VRA4 rats treated with GFP + PFF (DA 71.9 ± 1.10%, DA.VRA4 79.6 ± 0.77%) or ASYN + BSA (DA 77.3 ± 8.13%, DA.VRA4 73.8 ± 6.25%), the combination of *α*syn substrate and seed (ASYN + PFF) enhanced the loss of TH + fibres (DA 58.7 ± 2.74%, DA.VRA4 49.3 ± 2.86%) (Fig. 3A, B, Supplementary Fig. 4A, B). The neurodegenerative effect of seeded *α*syn was significantly enhanced compared to the control groups in DA.VRA4, but not DA rats (Fig. 3A, B), indicating that lower antigen presentation capacity mediated by *Mhc2ta* in the DA.VRA4 strain increases the susceptibility to *α*syn-seeded degeneration of dopaminergic striatal projection fibres.

In line with the data on denervation, the DA.VRA4 strain was also more susceptible to dopaminergic neurodegeneration determined by stereological cell counts, with a significant cell loss in the ipsilateral vs. contralateral SN under all three experimental conditions (ASYN + BSA $p < 0.05$; GFP + PFFs $p < 0.01$; ASYN + PFF $p < 0.01$) (Fig. 3D). In contrast, only the combination of rAAV6-*α*syn and PFFs resulted in significant cell loss in DA rats (ASYN + PFF $p < 0.01$, Fig. 3D). Thus, while dopaminergic nigral cell loss can be induced by viral over-expression of *α*syn or by exposure to PFFs alone in DA.VRA4 rats, a combination resulting in enhanced *α*syn pathology (see above) is required for DA rats.

Loss of nigrostriatal dopaminergic fibres and cell somas is considered to be preceded by axonal dysfunction. Therefore, TH+ axonal swellings

were quantified in the striatum and related to the remaining dopaminergic cell somas to account for prior loss of cells and their axons (Fig. 3E). The load of axonal swellings was dependent on *α*syn transgene expression, and were observed in rats receiving rAAV- *α*syn in combination with either BSA or PFFs. Rats exposed to PFFs alone displayed little axonal swellings (GFP + PFF vs ASYN + PFF, $p < 0.05$) in both strains (Fig. 3E). The similar load of axonal swellings at 8 weeks after vector delivery despite increased neurodegeneration in DA.VRA4 compared to DA rats might reflect a *Mhc2ta*-mediated resilience of dopaminergic cells to withstand axonal dysfunction.

Taken together, three hallmarks of dopaminergic neurodegeneration; loss of striatal fibres, nigral cell loss and axonal swellings; showed an enhanced neurodegeneration in the combined model compared to rAAV6-*α*syn or PFFs alone, which is in line with the observed seeding and propagation of *α*syn described above. Of note, lower *Mhc2ta* expression in the DA.VRA4 strain was associated to an increased susceptibility to both striatal denervation and nigral cell loss.

3.4. *Mhc2ta* alleles are associated with differential severity of *α*syn-induced motor deficits

To determine motor impairment, the use of ipsilateral and contralateral forelimb was assessed by the stepping test in animals at 2, 5 and 8 weeks after viral vector injections. DA.VRA4 rats displayed a progressive contralateral forelimb akinesia compared to sham controls (ASYN + PFF $p < 0.01$; GFP + PFF $p < 0.05$; ASYN + BSA $p = 0.05$), while no significant motor impairment was observed in DA rats (Fig. 3F, G).

Thus, dopaminergic neurodegeneration in terms of cell loss in the SN, reduced density of striatal fibres and presence of axonal swellings was reflected in significant motor impairment in DA.VRA4 rats with lower *Mhc2ta* expression compared to DA. In contrast, a combination of *α*syn and PFFs was required to induce dopaminergic cell loss in DA, and despite the presence of axonal swellings, the density of dopaminergic striatal fibres and motor function was preserved. This suggests that *Mhc2ta* regulates the threshold for axonal dysfunction and motor impairment in response to *α*syn aggregation and propagation.

3.5. Presence of MHCII+ cells in brain regions displaying *α*syn-seeded pathology

In order to characterize the local neuroinflammatory response associated to *α*syn inclusions, the anatomical distribution of MHCII+ cells in regions displaying *α*syn immunoreactivity was determined. In both DA and DA.VRA4 rats with PFF-seeded *α*syn pathology (ASYN + PFF), MHCII+ cells were abundant across the examined regions (Fig. 4A). The MHCII+ immunoreactivity matched the spatial distribution of *α*syn pathology (comparing Figs. 2B and 4A), confirming previous reports (Duffy et al., 2018). The anatomical areas mostly affected in both strains were the SN and the medial striatum (Fig. 4A1 to A12). Although less compared to the sites of injection, MHCII+ cells were detected throughout the brain, including the cerebellum, motor cortex, insular cortex, amygdala, thalamus and olfactory tubercle (Fig. 4A13–A24). Based on morphology (Sanchez-Guajardo et al., 2010; Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017), the MHCII+ cells displayed a predominant highly activated phenotype (large, dark cell bodies and thick, short processes) in the ASYN + PFF groups but a surveilling-like phenotype (long and thin processes, with or without many branches) in the GFP + PFF and ASYN + BSA groups (Supplementary Fig. 5A, B). In rats receiving GFP + PFF or ASYN + BSA, MHCII+ cells were confined to the injection sites and immediate surrounding areas (Supplementary Fig. 5). Compared to *α*syn or PFFs alone, the combined model thus induced a stronger microglial response with regard to abundance of MHCII+ cells and microglial morphology that colocalized with *α*syn inclusions.

Fig. 3. PFF-seeded *asyn* pathology induces fibre denervation and loss of cells in the dopaminergic system. **A.** Representative photomicrographs showing Tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) immunohistochemical staining throughout the brain of DA and DA.VRA4 rats after unilateral rAAV-*asyn* and PFF injections (ASYN + PFF). **B** and **C.** DA.VRA4, but not DA rats, with nigral expression of *asyn* and striatal injection of PFFs (ASYN + PFF) displayed significant TH + fibre loss in the striatum compared to (B) rats overexpressing GFP (GFP + PFF); Two-way ANOVA; Group: $F_{(3,22)} = 3.37$, $p = 0.04$, Levels $F_{(2,636,51,98)} = 0.92$, $p = 0.42$, Interaction $F_{(9,66)} = 0.37$, $p = 0.95$, and (C) rats receiving striatal injection of BSA (ASYN + BSA); Two-way ANOVA; Group: $F_{(3,24)} = 3.87$, $p = 0.022$, Levels $F_{(2,063,49,52)} = 5.12$, $p = 0.009$, Interaction $F_{(9,72)} = 0.65$, $p = 0.75$. Data are presented as % of optical density in the contralateral side and expressed as mean \pm SEM. **D.** DA.VRA4 rats display enhanced susceptibility to nigral TH + cell loss compared to DA rats. Stereological cell counts performed at 8 weeks post PFF/BSA injections. Two-way ANOVA; Group: $F_{(5,30)} = 1.95$, $p = 0.02$, Levels $F_{(2,063,49,52)} = 5.12$, $p = 0.009$, Interaction $F_{(9,72)} = 0.65$, $p = 0.75$. **E.** Nigral overexpression of *asyn* significantly enhances the load of axonal swellings in the striatum in both DA and DA.VRA4 rats receiving striatal injections of PFFs. One-way ANOVA; $F_{(5,29)} = 4.48$, $p = 0.004$. **F** and **G.** DA.VRA4, but not DA, rats display forelimb akinesia in the stepping test when subjected to the combined model (ASYN + PFF) as well as (F) PFFs alone (GFP + PFF) or (G) only *asyn* overexpression (ASYN + BSA). Two-way ANOVA; Group: $F_{(5,28)} = 3.21$, $p = 0.02$, Time $F_{(1,941,54,35)} = 3.11$, $p = 0.05$, Interaction $F_{(10,56)} = 1.24$, $p = 0.29$. Results from post-hoc groups comparison (Tukey's test) are reported as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

A

B

(caption on next page)

Fig. 4. Antigen-presenting MHCII⁺ cells are localized in *pasyn* pathology-affected brain regions. A. DA and DA.VRA4 rats injected with rAAV-*asyn* and PFFs (ASYN + PFF) display MHCII⁺ cells in regions affected by *pasyn* pathology; 3 striatal (A1–A6) and 3 nigral (A7–A12) levels, cerebellum (A13, A16), motor cortex (A14, A17), insular cortex (A15, A18), olfactory tubercle (A19, A22), amygdala (A20, A23) and thalamus (A21, A24). Scale bar = 25 μ m B. Significantly higher numbers of MHCII⁺ cells were found for DA.VRA4 compared to DA rats in the striatum (upper graph) when injected with ASYN + PFF and in the substantia nigra (SN, lower graph) when injected with ASYN + BSA. Average number of MHCII⁺ cells per region of interest (ROI) on the ipsilateral side 8-weeks after rAAV injection are shown. Two-way ANOVA; Striatum: Group $F_{(5,26)} = 21.59$ $p < 0.0001$, Side $F_{(1,26)} = 138.2$ $p < 0.0001$, Interaction $F_{(5,26)} = 14.93$ $p < 0.0001$; SN: Group $F_{(5,28)} = 8.339$ $p < 0.0001$, Side $F_{(1,28)} = 172.5$ $p < 0.0001$, Interaction $F_{(5,28)} = 8.713$ $p < 0.0001$. Results from post-hoc group comparisons (Tukey's test) are report as follows: $p < 0.05$ * between strains, $p < 0.05$ & within DA strain, $p < 0.05$ # within DA.VRA4 strain, $p < 0.01$ ** between strains, $p < 0.01$ && within DA strain, $p < 0.01$ ## within DA.VRA4 strain, $p < 0.0001$ **** between strains, $p < 0.0001$ &&& within DA strain, $p < 0.0001$ #### within DA.VRA4 strain. C. (Top graph) Unilateral injection of rAAV-GFP + PFF did not induce a differential serum cytokine profile. (Middle graph), ASYN + BSA induced increased IL-8 serum levels in DA.VRA4 compared to DA rats ($p = 0.04$), and (Bottom graph) ASYN + PFF induced increase of IL-2 ($p = 0.004$) and TNF α ($p = 0.03$) in serum from DA.VRA4 compared to DA rats. Unpaired t-test, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

3.6. Lower *Mhc2ta* levels is associated with increased number of MHCII⁺ cells and dopaminergic neurodegeneration

MHCII immunoreactive cells have been associated with accumulation of *asyn* inclusions and to the degree of neurodegeneration (Duffy et al., 2018). Previously we have shown that DA.VRA4 rats with reduced antigen presentation capacity present an increased number of striatal MHCII⁺ cells in response to high levels of *asyn* overexpression and striatal dopaminergic fibre loss (Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017). To determine the effect of reduced antigen presentation capacity in the number of MHCII⁺ cells in the presence of *asyn* substrate and seed, we performed semi-quantitative analysis of MHCII⁺ in the striatum and SN. At 8 weeks post unilateral rAAV6 injection, MHCII⁺ cells were observed in the ipsilateral striatum of all groups (ASYN + PFF, GFP + PFF and ASYN + BSA). The abundance of MHCII⁺ cells in striatum and SN was similar between rats receiving *asyn* only as substrate (ASYN + BSA) or as seed (GFP + PFF). In the ASYN + PFF groups, more MHCII⁺ cells were observed in the ipsilateral striatum, and were also present in the contralateral striatum, with significantly higher numbers in DA.VRA4 compared to DA rats (131.6 ± 15.20 vs 92.11 ± 17.82 , $p < 0.01$, Fig. 4B). These results show that seeded *asyn* pathology enhances the inflammatory response with regard to MHCII⁺ cells in the striatum and SN and is associated to an increased number of MHCII⁺ cells in rats with lower *Mhc2ta* transcriptional activity. The higher number of MHCII⁺ cells in DA.VRA4 rats is paralleled by increased *asyn* pathology and neurodegeneration compared to DA rats, which might reflect a compensatory mechanism where low *Mhc2ta* expression result in increased activation and recruitment of antigen-presenting cells contributing to neurodegeneration.

3.7. MHCII⁺ cells are associated with *asyn* pathology

We have recently demonstrated that DA.VRA4 microglia express lower levels of MHCII relative to Iba1 due to lower *Mhc2ta* levels (Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017). To determine whether the levels of MHCII affect the interaction between Iba1⁺ cells and *pasyn*, we analysed MHCII immunoreactivity in the striatum and SN of DA and DA.VRA4 rats receiving ASYN + PFF (Fig. 5). We found that in both strains, MHCII⁺ cells were located in close proximity to *pasyn* immunoreactive cells and inclusions in the striatum as well as SN. In several instances MHCII immunoreactivity co-localized with *pasyn* (Fig. 5), indicative of MHCII⁺ cells being active in the local response to *pasyn*. Notably, MHCII⁺ cells co-localizing with *pasyn* had a lower Iba-1 immunoreactivity, a hypertrophic cell body and an amoeboid morphology, suggesting that MHCII⁺ cells could be actively involved in the clearing and transfer of *asyn*.

3.8. Lower expression of *Mhc2ta* is associated with a higher a pro-inflammatory peripheral cytokine profile in response to *asyn*

To establish the *Mhc2ta*-mediated effects on the peripheral immune response to PFF-seeded *asyn* pathology, an inflammatory profile was determined using a cytokine- and chemokine panel (IFN γ , IL-1B, IL-2, IL-

4, IL-5, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL-12, TNF α) in serum at 8 weeks after vector injections. In the ASYN + PFF group, DA.VRA4 rats had higher levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines compared to DA (Fig. 4C). These included TNF α , a cytokine involved in systemic inflammation and implicated in multiple signalling pathways promoting exacerbation of the inflammatory response (0.65 ± 0.055 vs. 0.45 ± 0.044 , $p < 0.05$) and IL-2, a cytokine involved in inducing tolerance and immunity primarily via direct effects on T-cells (0.81 ± 0.030 vs. 0.67 ± 0.009 , $p < 0.05$) (Fig. 4C). After ASYN + BSA, IL-8, a proinflammatory mediator increased after oxidative stress, was significantly higher in DA.VRA4 compared to DA rats (0.77 ± 0.041 vs. 0.65 ± 0.020 , $p < 0.05$) (Fig. 4C). These results indicate that lower expression of *Mhc2ta* and MHCII in the DA.VRA4 strain induces a more pro-inflammatory peripheral cytokine profile compared to DA in response to intracranial *asyn*-seeded pathology.

4. Discussion

In this study, we show that allelic variants in the major regulator of MHCII expression, the *Mhc2ta* gene, are associated with different susceptibility to *asyn*-seeded pathology in a rat PD model. The effects are seen on a range of pathological processes, including the extent of *asyn* seeding and propagation, *pasyn* inclusion formation, local immune micro-environment, peripheral cytokine profile, dopaminergic neurodegeneration and motor dysfunction. Common variants in the human *MHC2TA* gene have been found to be associated to human complex inflammatory diseases (Swanberg et al., 2005). Taken together, these results make antigen presentation and the human *MHC2TA* gene highly relevant to investigate in relation to PD risk, as well as the progressive neuropathology and motor symptoms observed in PD patients.

Common variants in the HLA region, encoding MHCII molecules, are associated with PD risk (Wissemann et al., 2013; Lampe et al., 2003; Kannarkat et al., 2015; Hill-Burns et al., 2011; Hamza et al., 2010) and MHCII⁺ cells are present in the vicinity of *asyn* in PD brains (Croisier et al., 2005) as well as in PD models based on *asyn*-overexpression (Sanchez-Guajardo et al., 2010; Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017) and striatal injection of PFFs (Duffy et al., 2018). In addition, circulating CD4⁺ T-lymphocytes that react to *asyn* presented on MHCII are found in PD patients (Sulzer et al., 2017). These findings give strong support to a functional link between *asyn* pathology and MHCII-mediated antigen presentation. Despite the fact that *Mhc2ta* is the major regulator of MHCII in antigen-presenting cells, and has been shown to be required for *asyn*- and PFF-induced activation of microglia and resulting neurodegeneration (Williams et al., 2018), the role of human *MHC2TA* in PD susceptibility remains elusive. *MHC2TA* loss-of function mutations result in bare lymphocyte syndrome (BLS) and combined immunodeficiency (Steimle et al., 1993). In line with this, *mhc2ta* knock-out mouse models display an almost complete absence of MHCII and a dysfunctional adaptive immune system (Chang et al., 1996) which severely impacts studies on the role of antigen presentation in disease processes. Therefore, we have chosen to use the VRA4-congenic rat model where natural allelic variants in the *Mhc2ta* gene give rise to differential *Mhc2ta* and MHCII expression between DA.VRA4 and DA rats (Harnesk

Fig. 5. Iba1+/MHCII+ cells with reactive morphology are associated to inclusions and deposits of *αsyn*. Representative images of Iba1+/MHCII+ cells close to or overlapping with *αsyn* immunoreactive cells and/or deposits in A. striatum (ST) and B. substantia nigra (SN). Cells with advanced *αsyn* pathology were frequently seen to be completely enclosed or engulfed by one or several Iba1+/MHCII+ but not Iba1+/MHCII- cells (stars). *αsyn* dot-like inclusions were also observed inside Iba1+/MHCII+ cells (arrowheads).

et al., 2008). Employing this model, we recently showed that *Mhc2ta* regulates α syn-induced microglial activation, dopaminergic neurodegeneration and motor deficits in a rAAV-based PD model, with lower *Mhc2ta* expression levels being associated to increased neuroinflammation, neurodegeneration and motor impairment (Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017). The data presented here adds on to the previous findings and shows that natural genetic variants of *Mhc2ta*; in addition to regulating dopaminergic neurodegeneration and the subsequent development of motor deficits in response to α syn, is promoting a proinflammatory micro- and peripheral environment and impacts another key aspect of PD; propagation of α syn pathology.

In conjunction with α syn pathology, there is increasing evidence of a coexistent activation of microglia, and this activation is proposed to be α syn-conformation dependent (Duffy et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2013). The interplay between α syn and microglia could also be bidirectional, since altering the activation state of microglia using LPS or IL-4 was recently reported to affect the amount of α syn in dopaminergic neurons (George et al., 2019). A subset of MHCII-expressing microglia has been reported to attenuate neurodegenerative diseases (Mittal et al., 2019; Mathys et al., 2017) and studies in α syn overexpression models have shown that activation of microglia requires MHCII (Harms et al., 2013). Furthermore, DA.VRA4 rats, that display lower but physiological MHCII levels due to genetic variants in the *Mhc2ta* gene, have a highly activated microglial profile in striatum and SN in response to human WT α syn overexpression in SN (Jimenez-Ferrer et al., 2017). The role of microglia and of *Mhc2ta* as a key factor regulating α syn pathology is also supported by knockout and gene silencing models in mice (Williams et al., 2018). Since *Mhc2ta* levels that regulate antigen-presenting capacity have been shown to modulate immune responses and severity of α syn pathology, *Mhc2ta* is a promising immunomodulator in PD.

To address the *Mhc2ta*-mediated effects on the inflammatory micro-environment as well as transfer and propagation of α syn, we employed a new PD model in rats combining low α syn transgene expression in SN with injections of PFFs in the striatum. The combination of low titre rAAV6 to overexpress human α syn prior to the injection of human PFFs has previously been shown to result in a more efficient model for the spreading of α syn pathology compared to transgene or PFFs alone (Thakur et al., 2017). However, in that study, the delivery of rAAV6 vectors and PFFs was done to the same brain region and therefore the local responses can be attributed to both the mechanical injury, viral vector and PFFs. Here we used a similar approach but instead injected the PFFs to dopaminergic terminals in striatum 2 weeks after the rAAV6 injection in the SN. At this time point, the transgene expression is established throughout the nigrostriatal pathway (Decressac et al., 2012) allowing assessment of PFF-seeded α syn pathology from the striatum. As controls, we exchanged either the transgene (GFP instead of α syn) or the seed (BSA instead of PFF).

While expression of human α syn in the SN without addition of PFFs (ASYN + BSA) resulted mainly in local α syn inclusions, the addition of PFFs to the striatum resulted in widespread and bilateral propagation of phosphorylated forms of α syn. This confirms the seeding capacity of PFFs on locally produced human α syn in our combined model. In addition, the lower extent of α syn inclusions in rats lacking substrate in the form of a human α syn transgene (GFP + PFF) confirms a more efficient recruitment of human compared to endogenous (rat) α syn to inclusions (Rey et al., 2016; Volpicelli-Daley et al., 2011; Peelaerts et al., 2015). The endpoint at 6 weeks post-PFF administration in this study was, however, quite short and it is possible that more α syn pathology would develop over time in the GFP + PFF groups. The combination of α syn and PFFs not only led to enhanced α syn propagation but also induced α syn inclusions similar to those described in PD patients. However, while the striatal α syn inclusion pattern was dominated by filiform and varicose neurites in DA rats, more Lewy neurite-like deposits were observed in DA.VRA4 rats with lower *Mhc2ta* levels. This highlights the importance of the local pro-inflammatory micro-environment, and specifically *Mhc2ta*, as a regulator or contributing factor to

α syn-induced pathology.

In addition to enhancing α syn pathology, the combination of human α syn substrate and seed (ASYN + PFF) led to a marked increase in MHCII+ cells in neurodegeneration-associated regions compared to only substrate (ASYN + BSA) or seed (GFP + PFF). These results suggest that the increase in MHCII+ cells is a response to seeded α syn pathology and not to rAAV6 or PFFs injections alone. The observed spatial colocalization of Iba1+/MHCII+ cells displaying an amoeboid and hypertrophic morphology with α syn immunoreactive inclusions and intracellular punctuate α syn staining indicates that microglia can react to pathological forms of α syn and induce a phagocytic response resulting in presentation of α syn antigens on MHCII molecules. These results further suggest synucleinopathy-specific MHCII expression in Iba1 activated cells. Notably, DA.VRA4 rats displayed higher amounts of MHCII+ cells compared to DA, which might reflect a compensatory mechanism where a lower antigen-presenting capacity at the single cell level is coupled to an increased local population of MHCII+ cells.

One limitation of this study is the lack of discrimination between resident and infiltrating MHCII+ cells, and if these have different effects on α syn-induced responses. To determine the *Mhc2ta*-mediated effects on peripheral immune responses, we characterized the cytokine profile in serum at 8 weeks. In general, DA.VRA4 animals presented a more pro-inflammatory peripheral cytokine profile compared to DA with increased serum levels of TNF α and IL-2. The observed pro-inflammatory cytokine profile in DA.VRA4 rats is particularly interesting in light of the recent identification of α syn-reactive T lymphocytes in the blood of PD patients (Sulzer et al., 2017). It is important to note that this study did not address if the peripheral immune response is a consequence of the ongoing neurodegenerative process or a contributing factor to it. Nor did it assess local or peripheral T lymphocyte profiles, which requires analyses of lymphocytes in brain, cerebrospinal fluid and blood. The present study, however, shows that the more pro-inflammatory peripheral profile and local immune micro-environment with higher number of activated microglia and MHCII+ cells in DA.VRA4 rats are associated to an increased vulnerability of dopaminergic neurons to degeneration. Suggested mechanisms behind this include beneficial effects of degradation of cells with α syn inclusions with respect to α syn pathology or spreading, but to a higher inflammatory cost resulting in neuronal damage and/or death. Alternatively, low expression of *Mhc2ta* could lead to insufficient levels of MHCII and an immunological imbalance favouring microglial activation and neurotoxic effects.

The important role of axonal degeneration in PD is reflected by a widespread axonal pathology in various regions of the brains in the early stages of the disease (Braak et al., 2003). The consequences of α syn-seeded pathology in rats with normal (DA) or low (DA.VRA4) *Mhc2ta* levels were therefore evaluated by loss of dopaminergic terminals in the striatum as well as by neuronal loss in SN. DA.VRA4 rats with lower *Mhc2ta* levels showed to be more susceptible to both axonal neurodegeneration and nigral cell loss. Rats of both strains displayed a 20–30% dopaminergic fibre loss when injected with human α syn only as seed (ASYN + BSA) or substrate (GFP + PFF). However, only DA.VRA4 rats displayed a significantly enhanced dopaminergic fibre loss by the combination of human α syn substrate and seed (ASYN + PFF). An increased dopaminergic neurodegeneration in terms of TH+ cells in SN was also observed for DA.VRA4 rats, with a significant cell loss in all groups (ASYN + PFF, ASYN + BSA and GFP + PFF) while DA only displayed a significant cell loss in the ASYN + PFF group. Thus, the increased α syn pathology seen in DA.VRA4 compared to DA rats was coupled to a greater extent of dopaminergic neurodegeneration in both the striatum and SN. Of note, a significant motor impairment in terms of contralateral forelimb akinesia was also observed in DA.VRA4, but not DA, rats. Taken together these results show increased α syn pathology, dopaminergic neurodegeneration and subsequent motor impairment in DA.VRA4 rats with low *Mhc2ta* expression.

Further experiments are needed to characterize the impact of *Mhc2ta*

on cellular and soluble peripheral immune profiles over time in response to α syn pathology, since both microglia and lymphocytes in DA.VRA4 rats might be primed by the lower expression levels of *Mhct2a* and display altered inflammatory profiles prior to transgene expression and injection of PFFs. However, the observed requirement of human α syn as a substrate and PFFs as a seed for widespread α syn pathology and dopaminergic neurodegeneration, in combination with increased dopaminergic susceptibility in the DA.VRA4 strain, strongly suggest *Mhct2a* as a regulator of both inflammation and neurodegeneration in PD-like α syn pathology.

5. Conclusions

By employing a seeding model recapitulating pathological hallmarks of PD including progressive and widespread propagation of α syn pathology, we found an important interaction between *Mhct2a* allelic variants, a pro-inflammatory response and an increased vulnerability to α syn-induced PD-like pathology in rats. Common variants in the human *MHC2TA* gene are associated to MHCII expression, and in light of these findings we propose antigen presentation and microglial activation as promising targets in the quest to modify PD susceptibility and progression.

6. Availability of data and material

All original data are available for publication. All submitted figures are original files.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2020.10.017>.

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